

INTEGRATED ANALYTICAL CHARACTERIZATION AND CONTAMINANT EVALUATION OF YAVATHI KIYAZHAM THROUGH FTIR, SEM, HPTLC, TLC, AND MICROBIAL & CHEMICAL SAFETY TESTS

T. Porkodi^{1*}, S. Shankar²

*¹PG Scholar, Post Graduate Department of Gunapadam (Siddha Pharmacology) Government
Siddha Medical College, Chennai.

²Guide- Professor, Post Graduate Department of Gunapadam (Siddha Pharmacology)
Government Siddha Medical College, The TamilNadu Dr.M.G.R. Medical University
Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.

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*Corresponding Author

T. Porkodi

PG Scholar, Post Graduate Department
of Gunapadam (Siddha Pharmacology)
Government Siddha Medical College,
Chennai.

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ABSTRACT

The *Siddha* system is one of the oldest systems of traditional medicine in the world. The *siddha* system of medicine is based on the principles of *Pancha Bootham* (five basic elements) 96 *Thathuva* (factors), *Arusuvai* (6 tastes) and *Mukkuttram* (3 humours). Peptic Ulcer Disease is a condition characterized by the presence of open sores (ulcers) that develop on the mucosal lining of the stomach. PUD affected about 5–10% of the population in the world. In *Siddha* medicine herbal decoction is considered one of the most effective dosage forms due to its rapid absorption and therapeutic efficacy. Siddha polyherbal formulation *Yavathi Kiyazham* indicated for *Gunmam*, i.e., Peptic Ulcer from the classical text "*Anubava Vaidhya Deva Ragasiyam*". The objective of this study is to standardize *Yavathi Kiyazham* in detail through FTIR, SEM, HPTLC, TLC and to screen for specific Pathogen, Pesticide residue, Aflatoxin, Analysis of heavy metal and microbial load. Analytical techniques play a vital role in ensuring the safety, efficacy and quality of herbal formulations and furthermore for global acceptance.

KEYWORDS: Instrumental analysis, *Gunmam*, *Yavathi Kiyazham*, Pesticide residue, Aflatoxin.

INTRODUCTION

The *Siddha* system is one of the oldest systems of traditional medicine in the world. The *siddha* system of medicine is based on the principles of *Panchabootham* (five basic elements) 96 *Thathuva* (factors), *Arusuvai* (6 tastes) and *Mukkuttram* (3 humours). Peptic ulcer disease refers to open sores or lesions that develop on the inner lining of the stomach or the upper part of the small intestine (duodenum), due to the action of stomach acid and pepsin.^[1] It is caused by *Helicobacter pylori* infection – the most common cause and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) – e.g., ibuprofen, aspirin. Stress, smoking, alcohol are the other causes. PUD affected about 5–10% of the population in the world.^[2]

Siddha polyherbal formulation *Yavathi Kiyazham* used for *Gunmam*, i.e., Peptic Ulcer from the classical text “*Anubava Vaidhya Deva Ragasiyam*”^[3] is taken for analysis. The objective of this study is to standardize *Yavathi Kiyazham* through modern instruments to identify functional groups, impurities, quality control, studying chemical and molecular structures. SEM is observing surface morphology, particle size, surface structure and material composition at micro/nano level. HPTLC is Identification and quality control of herbal, pharmaceuticals, etc. TLC is analytical technique used to separate, identify, and sometimes quantify the components in a mixture. Test for specific Pathogen *E. coli*, *Salmonella* spp. *S.aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is necessary to identify contaminations in a given sample. Screening for Pesticide residue (Organochlorine pesticides, Organophosphorus pesticides, Pyrethroidse) ensures safety of the drug. Analysis of heavy metal elements (like lead, mercury, cadmium, arsenic), Microbial contamination (Total bacterial count, Total fungal count), Test for Aflatoxins (B1,B2,G1,G2) are executed for YK and their results have been established.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Selection of the drug

“*Yavathi Kiyazham*” has been taken from the *Siddha* literature “*Anubava Vaidhya Deva Ragasiyam*”.^[3]

Table No. 01: Ingredients of the drug YK.

S.NO	NAME OF THE DRUG	SCIENTIFIC NAME	QUANTITY
1.	Yavathaaniyam	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	1 palam (35 gm)
2.	Aamanaku ver	<i>Ricinus communis</i>	1 palam (35 gm)
3.	Tharupai pul	<i>Desmostachya bipinnata</i>	1 palam (35 gm)
4.	Naanal ver	<i>Saccharum spontaneum</i>	1 palam (35 gm)
5.	Karumbu ver	<i>Saccharum officinarum</i>	1 palam (35 gm)
6.	Seerupeelai	<i>Aerva lanata</i>	1 palam (35 gm)
7.	Thannirvittan kizhangu	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>	1 palam (35 gm)
8.	Kadukai thol	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	1 palam (35 gm)

COLLECTION OF THE RAW DRUG

The raw drugs were bought from reputed and genuine raw drug store, Chennai, Tamil Nadu.

RECOGNITION AND AUTHENTICATION OF THE DRUG

All drugs were recognized and authenticated by Gunapadam experts and Botanist in Government Siddha Medical College, Arumbakkam Chennai. The identified product samples were maintained in the PG Gunapadam laboratory for future references. The selected drug has been submitted before the IAEC Government Siddha Medical College for pre-clinical analysis.

PURIFICATION OF THE DRUG

Purification process were done as per classical Siddha literature (Sarakkugalin suthi sei muraigal).^[4]

METHOD OF PREPARATION

All the drug will be taken in an equal quantity. Then the drugs will be pounded into a coarse powder. Finally, the prepared medicines will be stored in an air tight container. 30g of prepared chooranam will be added with 240ml of water and heated at low flame till the water condensed to 30ml.

STANDARDIZATION OF THE DRUG

Standardization of drugs means confirmation of its identity, Quality and purity. Standardization includes many studies such as FTIR, SEM, HPTLC, TLC. Screening for specific Pathogen, Pesticide residue and Aflatoxin, Analysis of heavy metal and microbial load are included in standardization. These analytical screening had been done at Noble laboratories Chennai.

FTIR ANALYSIS^[5]

Sample processed using Bruker Alpha-E by ATR module (attenuated total reflectance). Sample positioned on the Crystal platform with perfect alignment of keeping anvil in up position. To ensure that the sample makes good contact angle with the crystal prior to start of the IR radiation exposure. Spectra measurement was achieved with desired wavelength, and the corresponding observational peaks/ waves were recorded with wavenumber were subjected to further interpretation. Software used for the analysis is OPUS version 7 for functional group analysis. Signal detection processed through DTGS detector. Baseline correction adjusted as per the requirement.

SEM ANALYSIS^[6]

A SEM is essentially a high magnification microscope, which uses a focused scanned electron beam to produce images of the sample, both top-down and, with the necessary sample preparation, cross sections. The test sample powder was sputter coated with gold and viewed under SEM (FEI Quanta 200 FEG, Berlin, Germany) to determine the morphology at $\times 100,000$ magnification and the particle size at $\times 200,000$ magnification.

HPTLC ANALYSIS^[7]

HPTLC method is a modern sophisticated and automated separation technique derived from TLC. Pre-coated HPTLC graded plates and auto sampler was used to achieve precision, sensitive, significant separation both qualitatively and quantitatively. High performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC) is a valuable quality assessment tool for the evaluation of botanical materials efficiently and cost effectively. Thus this method can be conveniently adopted for routine quality control analysis. It provides chromatographic fingerprint of phytochemicals which is suitable for confirming the identity and purity of phytotherapeutics. Chromatogram Development - It was carried out in CAMAG Twin Trough chambers. Sample elution was carried out according to the adsorption capability of the component to be analyzed. After elution, plates were taken out of the chamber and dried.

Scanning - Plates were scanned under UV at 366nm. The data obtained from scanning were brought into integration through CAMAG software. Chromatographic fingerprint was developed for the detection of phytoconstituents present in each sample and their respective R_f values were tabulated.

TLC ANALYSIS^[8]

Test sample was subjected to thin layer chromatography (TLC) as per conventional one-dimensional ascending method using silica gel 60F254, 7X6 cm (Merck) were cut with ordinary household scissors. Plate markings were made with soft pencil. Micro pipette were used to spot the sample for TLC applied sample volume 10-micro liter by using pipette at distance of 1 cm at 5 tracks. In the twin trough chamber with the specified solvent system After the run plates are dried and was observed using visible light Short-wave UV light 254nm and light long-wave UV light 365 nm.

TEST FOR SPECIFIC PATHOGEN^[9]

Test sample was directly inoculated into the specific pathogen medium (EMB, DCC, Mannitol, Cetrinide) by pour plate method. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 - 72h for observation. Presence of specific pathogen identified by their characteristic colour with respect to pattern of colony formation in each differential media.

PESTICIDE RESIDUE^[10,11]

Test sample were extracted with acetone and followed by homogenization for brief period. Further filtration was allowed and subsequent addition of acetone to the test mixture. Heating of test sample was performed using a rotary evaporator at a temperature not exceeding 40°C until the solvent has almost completely evaporated. To the residue add a few milliliters of toluene and heat again until the acetone is completely removed. Resultant residue will be dissolved using toluene and filtered through membrane filter.

AFLATOXIN^[12]

Standard - Aflatoxin B1, Aflatoxin B2, Aflatoxin G1, Aflatoxin G2.

Solvent - Standard samples were dissolved in a mixture of chloroform and acetonitrile (9.8: 0.2) to obtain a solution having concentrations of 0.5 µg per ml each of aflatoxin B1 and aflatoxin G1 and 0.1 µg per ml each of aflatoxin B2 and aflatoxin G2.

Standard aflatoxin was applied on to the surface to pre coated TLC plate in the volume of 2.5 µL, 5 µL, 7.5 µL and 10 µL. Similarly, the test sample was placed and allow the spots to dry and develop the chromatogram in an unsaturated chamber containing a solvent system consisting of a mixture of chloroform, acetone and isopropyl alcohol (85: 10: 5) until the solvent front has moved not less than 15 cm from the origin. Remove the plate from the

developing chamber, mark the solvent front and allow the plate to air-dry. Locate the spots on the plate by examination under UV light at 365 nm.

ANALYSIS OF HEAVY METAL^[13]

Atomic Absorption Spectrometry (AAS) is a very common and reliable technique for detecting metals and metalloids in environmental samples. The total heavy metal content of the sample was performed by Atomic Absorption Spectrometry (AAS) Model AA 240 Series. In order to determine the heavy metals such as mercury, arsenic, lead and cadmium concentrations in the test item.

Sample Digestion - Test sample was digested with 1mol/L HCl for determination of arsenic and mercury. Similarly, for the determination of lead and cadmium the sample were digested with 1mol/L of HNO₃.

Standard Preparation - As & Hg- 100 ppm sample in 1mol/L HCl
Cd & Pb- 100 ppm sample in 1mol/L HNO₃

STERILITY TEST BY POUR PLATE METHOD^[14]

Objective - The pour plate techniques were adopted to determine the sterility of the product. Contaminated / unsterile sample (formulation) when come in contact with the nutrition rich medium it promotes the growth of the organism and after stipulated period of incubation the growth of the organism was identified by characteristic pattern of colonies. The colonies are referred to as Colony Forming Units (CFUs).

Methodology - Test sample was inoculated in sterile petri dish to which about 15 mL of molten agar 45°C were added. Agar and sample were mixed thoroughly by tilting and swirling the dish. Agar was allowed to completely gel without disturbing it. (about 10 minutes). Plates were then inverted and incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hours and further extended for 72 hrs for fungal growth observation. Grown colonies of organism was then counted and calculated for CFU.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FTIR ANALYSIS

Fig. No. 01: FT-IR SPECTRUM OF SAMPLE YK.

Table No. 02: FT-IR PEAK TABLE.

Peak Number	Range (cm-1)	Functional Group
1.	4000–3500	Hydroxyl (-OH), Amine (-NH) O-H stretching (alcohols, phenols), N-H stretching (amines)
2.	3500–3000	Alkyne (-C≡C-H), N-H stretch Terminal alkyne C-H, N-H stretch (amines, amides)
3.	3000–2500	C-H (Alkanes, Alkenes, Aromatics) C-H stretching (sp^3 , sp^2 hybridized carbons)
4.	2500–2000	Thiol (-SH), Carboxylic Acid (O-H broad) S-H stretch, Broad O-H stretch from acids
5.	2000–1500	C≡C, C≡N (Alkynes, Nitriles) Triple bond stretches (alkynes, nitriles)
6.	1500–1000	C=C (Aromatic, Alkene), C-O (Esters, Alcohols) Aromatic ring vibrations, C-O stretching in esters, ethers, and alcohols

SEM ANALYSIS

It was observed from the SEM analysis of YK that the average particle size of the sample ranges from 45.26 μm to 151.1 μm .

Fig. No: 02: SEM image of YK- Cluster.

Fig. No: 03: SEM image of YK- Categorised.

HPTLC & TLC ANALYSIS

HPTLC finger printing analysis of the sample reveals the presence of ten prominent peaks corresponds to the presence of versatile phytochemicals present with in it. The major Rf value of the peaks ranges from 0.01 to 0.92.

Fig. No: 04: TLC Visualization of YK at 366 nm.

Fig. No: 05 - 3D – Chromatogram.

Fig. No: 06: HPTLC finger printing of YK.

Table no: 03 - Peak table of phytocomponents of YK.

Peak	Start Rf	Start Height	Max Rf	Max Height	Max %	End Rf	End Height	Area	Area %
1	0.01	2.3	0.02	179.9	14.65	0.05	79.8	1493.2	6.98
2	0.05	82.6	0.07	161.3	13.14	0.09	2.8	1725.1	8.07
3	0.12	11.0	0.15	61.0	4.97	0.16	2.1	502.0	2.35
4	0.17	8.1	0.18	41.4	3.37	0.22	0.0	362.5	1.70
5	0.22	1.0	0.28	86.8	7.07	0.34	1.3	1533.4	7.17
6	0.34	0.3	0.43	444.5	36.21	0.51	6.8	9920.9	46.39
7	0.57	6.3	0.61	37.2	3.03	0.65	15.4	656.8	3.07
8	0.65	15.9	0.69	31.9	2.59	0.75	21.8	980.6	4.59
9	0.75	20.4	0.82	87.1	7.10	0.89	25.3	2894.2	13.53
10	0.92	32.2	0.97	96.4	7.85	1.01	1.4	1317.2	6.16

TEST FOR SPECIFIC PATHOGEN

No growth / colonies were observed in any of the plates inoculated with the test sample.

Table no: 04 - Results of test for specific pathogen in YK.

Organism	Specification	Result	Method
<i>E-coli</i>	Absent	Absent	As per AYUSH specification
<i>Salmonella</i>	Absent	Absent	
<i>Staphylococcus Aureus</i>	Absent	Absent	
<i>Pseudomonas Aeruginosa</i>	Absent	Absent	

Fig. No: 07: Culture plate with E-coli (EC) specific medium.

Fig. No: 08: Culture plate with Salmonella (SA) specific medium.

Fig. No: 09: Culture plate with Staphylococcus Aureus (ST) specific medium.

Fig. No: 10: Culture plate with Pseudomonas Aeruginosa (PS) specific medium.

PESTICIDE RESIDUE

The results showed that there were no traces of pesticides residues such as Organo chlorine, Organo phosphorus, Organo carbamates and pyrethroids in the sample provided for analysis. Whereas the sample reveals the presence of mild traces of Malathion at 50 µg/kg which belongs to the category of Organo Phosphorus Pesticide.

Table no: 05: Test Result Analysis of the Sample YK.

Pesticide Residue	Sample YK	AYUSH Limit (mg/kg)
I.Organo Chlorine Pesticides		
Alpha BHC	BQL	0.1mg/kg
Beta BHC	BQL	0.1mg/kg
Gamma BHC	BQL	0.1mg/kg
Delta BHC	BQL	0.1mg/kg
DDT	BQL	1mg/kg
Endosulphan	BQL	3mg/kg
II.Organo Phosphorus Pesticides		
Malathion	50 µg/kg	1mg/kg
Chlorpyriphos	BQL	0.2 mg/kg
Dichlorovos	BQL	1mg/kg
III. Organo carbamates		
Carbofuran	BQL	0.1mg/kg
III.Pyrethroid		
Cypermethrin	BQL	1mg/kg

BQL- Below Quantification Limit

AFLATOXIN

The results shown that there were no spots were being identified in the test sample loaded on TLC plates when compared to the standard which indicates that the sample were free from Aflatoxin B1, Aflatoxin B2, Aflatoxin G1 and Aflatoxin G2.

Table No. 06: Result of Aflatoxin test.

Aflatoxin	Sample YK	AYUSH Specification Limit
B1	Not Detected – Absent	0.5 ppm (0.5mg/kg)
B2	Not Detected – Absent	0.1 ppm (0.1mg/kg)
G1	Not Detected – Absent	0.5 ppm (0.5mg/kg)
G2	Not Detected – Absent	0.1 ppm (0.1mg/kg)

ANALYSIS OF HEAVY METAL

Results of the present investigation have clearly shown that the sample has no traces of heavy metal such as Mercury and Cadmium were as the sample evident the presence of Lead and Arsenic at 3.23 and 1.16 ppm levels.

Table No. 07: Test Report for Heavy Metal.

Name of the Heavy Metal	Absorption Max λ max	Result Analysis	Maximum Limit
Lead	217.0 nm	3.23	10 ppm
Arsenic	193.7 nm	1.16	3 ppm
Cadmium	228.8 nm	BDL	0.3 ppm
Mercury	253.7 nm	BDL	1 ppm

BDL- Below Detection Limit ppm – Parts per million

STERILITY TEST BY POUR PLATE METHOD

No growth / colonies was observed in any of the plates inoculates with the test sample.

Fig. No. 11: Results of sterility test by pour plate method for YK.

Table No. 08: Results of sterility test by pour plate method for YK.

Test	Result	Specification	As per AYUSH/WHO
Total Bacterial Count	Absent	NMT 105CFU/g	As per AYUSH specification
Total Fungal Count	Absent	NMT 103CFU/g	

CONCLUSION

Standardization is a preliminary step in the drug development process. For *Yavathi Kiyazham* (YK), this has been carried out in accordance with the analytical specifications. Based on the results obtained, preclinical in-vitro studies have been successfully conducted on this formulation, further in-vivo and clinical studies are necessary to confirm its therapeutic potential and efficacy.

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